

Review Article

G-D's Physics Points at the "End of Time": "Perfected Geulah State" of the Universe!?

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Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm based on a "time-sensitive" measurement of a predicted increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days' time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish's e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 29th Century's General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT)! This profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" ensues from the preceding "Paradigmatic Crisis" of the Old Paradigm – signified by the "theoretical inconsistency" between its two "pillars", e.g., GRT & QM, and its inability to account for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, assumed to be "caused" by an "undetectable" purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" concept (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all matter, but which failed to be detected experimentally for the past two decades)! In contrast, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm discovered a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe) at the incredible rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 (sec'), which creates an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! Based on "G-D's Physics" discovery of the UCP and associated "Universal Computational Formula" which completely unifies (for the first time in Physics) between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", it provides us with an alternative explanation for the origin- sustenance- ("dissolution")- and "development" of the entire physical universe: towards an "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of the universe! In the current article, direct empirical validation of two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is outlined which therefore provides science with an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe based on this singular UCP's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Postulate, and points at the feasibility of a new (exciting) conception of the UCP's "steering" of the universe towards an "End of Time: Perfected Geulah State", in which Science (and Humanity) will recognize the "Singularity", "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing this singular UCP, as well as Humanity's "Perfected Geulah" State!

Introduction

Scientific Inquiry (within any given discipline) is governed by empirical data and logical reasoning that can best explain that given data within a cohesive Theoretical Framework! However, the famous Philosopher of Science, Thomas Kuhn taught us that the evolution of such Scientific Inquiry (within a given scientific discipline) alternates between phases governed by a given "Standard Paradigm" in which such a given "Standard Paradigm" is capable of explaining all known data and phenomena, and an inevitable subsequent "Paradigmatic-Shift" into a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) which follows the appearance of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" within the Old "Standard Paradigm"; Such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" is characterized by the appearance of "theoretical inconsistencies" between the "foundations" of the Old "Standard Paradigm", such as for instance the apparent theoretical inconsistency that appeared between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory. In addition, a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" is also characterized by the principle inability of this Old "Standard Paradigm" to account for a key empirical phenomenon, such the inability of the Old 19th century's Newtonian Mechanics to empirically validate the existence of the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept which was key for Newto-

nian Mechanical Theoretical Framework?! Kuhn teaches us that alongside with the appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" for the Old "Standard Paradigm" (in this case Newtonian Mechanics) there emerges the "New Paradigm" (e.g., Relativity Theory) shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" (between Newtonian Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory), resolving the "unexplained empirical phenomenon" (e.g., Relativity Theory discarded the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept as "superfluous" or "non-existent!"); and most significantly identify and empirically validate at least one unique "Critical Prediction" of the "New Paradigm" – as more valid than the corresponding prediction of the "Old Paradigm": In the case of Einstein's General Relativity Theory (GRT) this unique "Critical Prediction" related to his prediction regarding the double-valued curvature of Mercury's perihelion's pathway around the Sun (e.g., due to the Sun's mass' curvature of Space-Time affecting Mercury's curved perihelion pathway); Indeed, once Einstein's double-valued Mercury's perihelion pathway (around the Sun) unique "Critical Prediction" was validated by Eddington during the famous 1919 Solar Eclipse – Einstein's GRT "triumphed" and was accepted as the New Scientific Paradigm for 20th century Theoretical Physics!

We stand at an equivalent (historic) "juncture" in which the Old "Material-Causal" (Standard Paradigm) of GRT and Quantum Mechanics (QM), has reached a clear "Paradigmatic-Crisis", e.g., due the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between these two GRT & QM "pillars" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm seem "theoretically inconsistent": this is due to the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict insistence upon the "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) for the transmission of any signal (or information) across space and time, as opposed to QM's (empirically validated) "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon which indicates that a measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (space-energy, time-mass) value/s, e.g., apparently contradicting GRT's SLB fundamental constraint?! Additionally, there exists a key "unexplained empirical phenomenon" relating to the universe's accelerated rate of expansion which can only be explained by GRT's assuming of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts which are assumed to comprise up to 90% of all the mass and energy in the universe – but yet failed to be detected (despite numerous experimental attempts) for the past two decades?! Indeed, two highly influential scientific articles recently published by Scientific American begin questioning the validity of these purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT and QM has reached a state of "Paradigmatic-Crisis" which has indeed led to the discovery of a New "Computational Unified Field Theory" (CUFT), recently termed: "G-D's Physics" (See exhaustive Bentovish References) shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM! The manner in which this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is able to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM is based on its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which is postulated to simultaneously compute all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, e.g., including their four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – at an unfathomably rapid rate of "c²/h" = 1.36-50 (sec)! This produces an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at every such "minimal time point", e.g., with all such exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames! Additionally, as part of the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s, it also computes "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) relativistic "object" or subatomic "particle" computation, as well as "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) computation of more than one spatial-temporal "object"/"particle" point at any given UF's frame/s, e.g., giving rise to the (relativistic or subatomic) "wave" phenomenon! Thus, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's theoretical framework is capable of explicating the embedding of any SSP "particle", e.g., including two "entangled particles" as integral parts of the broader "MST" "wave" phenomenon – which are both embedded within the "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) UCP's computation of the entire UF's frame/s (e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame)! Viewed from this novel higher-ordered perspective of the UCP's EST computation of all exhaustive spatial temporal pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as embedding within it both the SST "entangled particles" and the broader MST "wave" computation allows for this New "G-D's Physics" to resolve the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM – while pointing at the much more exhaustive theoretical framework of the UCP's production of the series of UF's frame/s!

Indeed, a major discovery made by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the complete unification – not only between GRT & QM, but also between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as well as between the four basic Forces!) within a newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which explicates the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This major UCF discovery stems from "G-D's Physics" novel computation of these four basic physical features as

underlie by the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency": According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm the UCP computes for each given (relativistic or subatomic) object – its degree of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") relative to two possible "Framework" levels, i.e., relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "object" itself (i.e., internal composition), which gives rise to those four basic physical features; That is, when the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" measures of any given object this yields the two corresponding physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas when the UCP computes the two "Object" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" measures this produces the two corresponding physical features of "mass" and "time"! Based on these new (and exciting) UCP's computational definitions of these four basic physical features (given below) the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was able to integrate them as secondary computational features of the same singular higher-ordered UCP, thereby giving rise to this profound novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)!

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF):

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} \text{UF's } \{n \dots n \dots n\} [Px]_{(a \dots z)} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

Method & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i) - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i \dots n)] \leq n * h [\{UF's(i \dots n)\}]$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value."G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [1].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction [1], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?! In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its abovementioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical). This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements! Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [2], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, [3,4], higher dimension gravity, [5], a new boson, [6], and the quasi-free hypothesis π^+ [7], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashanah" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary)

rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Hence, to the extent that these two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm are empirically validated, then this will convince the Scientific Community that the New "G-D's Physics" has to be accepted as a satisfactory New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics! Based on such direct empirical validation of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a discussion ensues of the manner in which "G-D's Physics" newly discovered singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) is capable of computing every exhaustive spatial pixel or "object" (e.g., including "human-beings" as opposed to "non-human": "inanimate" material object/s, as well as "animate": plants and animals) – based on a further discovery of the UCP's "Gimateria" (i.e., Hebrew letters' numerical values) of each object's five "secondary-essential" "Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (HCD's) of: "Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod" (e.g., each of them comprising "ten zero's" out of the "fifty zero's" comprising the incredible rate of the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe: $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ (sec)! As will be discussed, this entirely new conception of the manner in which this singular, higher-ordered UCP computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's "object" in the universe is "non-material"; i.e., exemplifying the "translation" of the fundamental new "building-blocks" ("or "Atoms" – metaphorically) of the entire physical universe from the Hebrew letters' "Gimatria" (numerical values, also associated with these five "secondary-essential" HCD's corresponding "ten zero's") to the production of each ("human" or "non-human") object's unique physical characteristics! Indeed, it is shown that this novel manner in which the UCP is seen to compute the specific physical characteristics of each individual (unique "human" or "non-human") "object" is a part and parcel of the UCP's overall "Blueprint Plan" of steering the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" material composition through its "animate": "plants", "animals", human-beings – leading to the fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of a "Moral", "Spiritual" and even "Physical" "Perfected" state of the universe in which the singu-

larity of this “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR), e.g., characterized by “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” being recognized (and accepted) by Science and Humanity (more generally)!

“G-D’s Physics Points at the “End of Time”: “Perfected Geulah State” of the Universe!

Based on the (above) empirical validation of two unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm is accepted as the New (satisfactory) Paradigm of 21st century Theoretical Physics! It completely revises our most basic conceptions of the origin- nature- dynamics- evolution- and “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of the universe’s existence and development! First, we realize that the physical universe was not created or “caused” by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event! This is because the Big-Bang Model (which is a part of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm) assumes a “cause and effect” physical relationship/s between such a hypothetical “Big-Bang” nuclear event and its “creation” (or “causing”) of all the suns, galaxies, mass, energy – and even “time”!? But, as we’ve seen, according to the New “A-Causal Computation” “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm, there cannot exist any such “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or even in any (other) consecutive UF’s frames (e.g., due to the singular “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle’s” simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each such consecutive UF’s frame/s, and the complete “dissolution” of the whole entire universe – “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s)! Moreover, based on the two earlier mentioned (profound) “Theoretical Postulates” of the “Computational Invariance Principle” and “Universal Consciousness Principle” we realize that since it is only this singular higher-ordered UCP – that exists both “during” its computation of each consecutive UF’s frame/s, and also (solely) exists “in-between” any two such “consecutive” UF’s frame/s, therefore only this singular UCP (truly) exists whereas the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive) spatial pixels’ (associated four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”) – exists only as a “transient” and “phenomenal” manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCP! We therefore, begin realizing that the whole existence and development of the universe – may only be based on the UCP’s own intrinsic characteristics, which has led to the discovery of its “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions” (THCD’s) that describes the UCP’s “Blueprint Plan” for the creation and development of the entire physical universe towards the fulfillment of its Ultimate Geulah Goal! We see, that due to “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm there cannot exist any “material-causal” physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in one UF’s frame/s and any other consecutive UF’s frame, and therefore that one UF’s frame cannot “create” or even “affect” any subsequent UF’s frame/s – and hence, that the development of the entire physical universe may only be based on the UCP’s singular higher-ordered THCD’s “Blueprint Plan” for the development of the universe towards its “Ultimate Geula Goal” Perfected (Moral, Spiritual and even Physical) State!

We therefore, obtain an entirely new conception of the origin- existence- development- and “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of the entire physical universe! The universe was not “accidentally” created by a “Big-Bang” nuclear event, but was rather “pre-planned” based on this singular “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) “Blueprint Plan” (UCP) to develop from “inanimate” matter, through “animate”: “plants, animals, and human-beings – all geared towards the fulfillment of the UCP’s “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of bringing Humanity (and hence the whole universe) to it’s a recognition of the singularity of this UCP as the sole Reality underlying the entire physical universe, and respecting Its intrinsic Characteristics of “Morality”, “Goodness”, “Peace” and “Harmony”, which would lead Humanity to lead such a “Moral”, “Peaceful” and “Harmonious” Life! Viewed from such a “Geulah-Goal Perfected” (e.g., Morally, Spiritually and even

Physically) “Blueprint Plan” perspective, we understand that the whole evolution of the physical universe, and of Humanity within it, e.g., playing a “key central role” as the “Apex” of the development of the whole universe towards Humanity’s “Perfected Geulah State” – does not occur based on any “accidental” or “random” “material-causal” physical interactions, but is rather “directed” based on the UCP’s Pre-planned “Blueprint Plan” towards achieving this “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of a “Perfected: “Morally”, “Spiritually” and even “Physically”!

Therefore, the pertinent question arises: what may be the “beginning” and “end” of the universe – in “space” and “time”, according to this new (empirically proven) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm? In order to answer this important question, lets revert back to the (novel) “computational definitions” of “G-D’s Physics” “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP): As shown (previously), according to “G-D’s Physics”, the UCP (simultaneously) computes for all exhaustive spatial pixels, the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “time” and “mass”; Specifically, the UCP’s computation of the “time” (value) for every exhaustive spatial pixel is computed as an “Object-inconsistent”(e.g., degree of “change”) computed for each “object” across a series of UF’s frame/s! But, based on “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm’s realization that there cannot exist any (“material-causal”) physical interaction between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF’s frame/s, and therefore that there cannot exist any “material-causal” physical relationship/s between one UF’s frame/s and another UF’s frame/s; we reached the inevitable conclusion that the UCP’s computation- sustenance- and evolution- of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe (as well as the entire universe) can only be based and derived from the UCP’s “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions” (e.g., which are integrated based on these “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions”: “Universal Computational Formula”, THCD-UCF)! Indeed, as outlined (previously), an examination of these THCD’s of the UCP indicate that they exhibit and manifest the UCP’s “Blueprint Plan” for “steering” the entire universe from “inanimate matter”, through “animate”: “plants”, “animals” and “human-beings” towards manifesting the UCP’s “Ultimate Geulah Goal”! Hence, we can see, that this whole “progression” (or “development”) of the whole physical universe (e.g., from “inanimate” matter, through “animate”: plants, animals, and human-beings) towards the “Ultimate Geulah Goal” constitutes – and in fact “spans” the entire “time” of the universe’s “origination”, “sustenance”, “development”, and “attainment” of this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” State of the universe! Perhaps utilizing the earlier mentioned Cinematic Film Metaphor” for Attainment of the “Geulah Goal Perfected State” will assist us in better understanding the true nature of “time” – including the “beginning” and “end” of the universe’s “time” (according to the New “G-D’s Physics Scientific Paradigm)! If we were to imagine a certain film depiction presenting the creation of a “physical universe”: comprising of all “inanimate”: rocks, stones, marbles, mountains, planets, suns and galaxies etc., then the development of all “animate”: plants, animals and finally human-beings – leading to Humanity’s progression from a state of “strife and conflict” to a “Perfected State” of “Peace & Harmony”, “Goodness & Morality”! We could infer from looking at such a (special) “Film-Plot” a few pertinent points: a) we realize that (long before) the actual “execution” of this Film, the Producer of the Film has to possess a “Complete Screenplay” or “Blueprint Plan” for the “build-up” of this (apparently) “physical universe”, including all of the “situations” and “occurrences” happening in the Film! b) we also realize that the whole “time-span” of this (apparently) “physical universe development”, e.g., leading up to the “Perfected State of Humanity” (e.g., “Geulah”) – say, “twenty-years” is all “encapsulated” or “manifests” within the entire “series of film-frames”! c) we must (also) realize that this Producer must have “Pre-planned” the whole progression of the Film – through a particular “Screenplay” which has been written to “convey” or reach a specific “motto” or “message”, i.e., such as a “happy ending”, or a certain “Moral message”! How is this “Cinematic

Film Metaphor” relevant for our understanding of the manner in which the singular higher-ordered UCP has “Pre-planned” and is (continuously) “computing” and “steering” the whole physical universe towards its “Ultimate Geulah Perfected State”? Well, this Cinematic-Film Metaphor clearly teaches us, that in the same way that we realized the whole “Film progression” (or “Film plot”) must have been “Pre-planned” by the Producer of the Film – before starting to “execute” its “filming”; “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm asserts that the singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) must have had a “Complete Blueprint Plan” for the whole development of the physical universe: from “inanimate” matter, through “animate”: plants, animals, and human-beings leading up to the UCP’s “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal, before the actual “initial creation” of the universe! Hence, according to “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm, not only the physical universe – was not created by any (“random”) “Big-Bang” nuclear event (as clearly proven above and previously), but (in fact) the initial “Creation” of the physical universe has “begun” with the UCP’s “Initial Key Three Hierarchical Computational Dimensions” (IKTHCD, as published previously)! These IKTHCD comprise: a) The “Wisdom” (“המחכה”) / “Free-Will” HCD, in which the singular higher-ordered UCP has set the “Vision” (and “Wish”) of creating an apparently “physical universe” that seems “separate” (and “independent”) from this singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR or UCP) that would lead up to the UCR’s “Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal” (of a Humanity that recognizes and realizes- the “Oneness” and “Inseparability” of all human-beings from this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is characterized by such “sublime” characteristics as “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!) b) “Geulah Blueprint Plan”: “Reversed Time Geulah Goal” HCD, which “translates” this (general) “Ultimate Geulah Goal” Vision of the UCR into a detailed “Blueprint Plan” for the whole creation, sustenance and evolution of the whole physical universe: from “inanimate” matter, through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings – and up to its “culmination” in the fulfillment of the UCR’s “Ultimate Geulah Goal”! c) “Consistency Computation”/”תעד” HCD, which actually details the UCP’s Computations of the “Physical”, “Moral-Conscious”, and “Geulah-Directed” aspects of the “origination”- “sustenance”- (“dissolution”)- “evolution” of the entire physical universe towards its “fulfillment” of the UCR’s “Ultimate Geulah Goal” State (of the universe)! Hence, we can see that the universe’s “creation” was preceded by these three IKTHCD – and in fact realize that not only was the entire physical universe’s “creation”, “sustenance”, “development” and “Ultimate Geulah Goal” has been “Pre-planned” (meticulously) by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR; but even the ongoing and continuous “creation” (computation) of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, “dissolution”, “re-computation” and “development” (e.g., towards that “Ultimate Geulah Goal State” of the universe) is also completely dependent upon- and executed- by this singular UCP’s three IKTHCD “Blueprint Plan” (i.e., so many “trillions” of times per second: $c2/h = 1.35 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ sec}^{-1}$!) The Cinematic-Film Metaphor also assists us in realizing that in the same manner that the whole “time-span” of the (above particular) “Universal-Film” may be of a “twenty-years” “time-interval”, and that this “time-span” “encapsulates” the entire “time” of this “time-interval”; so “G-D’s Physics” asserts that the entire “time-span” of the whole universe’s development from these initial three IKTHCD’s through the appearance of the (increasingly “more expansive” forms of this singular higher-ordered UCP of) “inanimate” matter, then “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings – and up to fulfillment of the universe’s Ultimate “Geulah-Goal” State of the universe, also “encapsulates” the totality of the universe’s “time-interval”! Moreover, since we’ve realized that prior to the actual “creation” of the physical universe, there must have existed a “Complete Geulah-Goal Blueprint Plan” for the “execution”- “development” and “fulfillment” of this “Geulah-Goal Perfected State” of the universe (e.g., and all of the preceding “steps” leading to this Perfected State); and specifically, our realization that based on “G-D’s Physics two (profound) “Computational Invariance Principle” and associated “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) Theoretical Postu-

lates, that the entire physical universe doesn’t exist “independently” of this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCR, but is rather only a “transient-phenomenal” manifestation of this singular UCR; therefore, we reach the inevitable conclusion that the whole universe is being continuously “directed” towards the “fulfillment” of its “Ultimate Geula Goal Perfected State”! Finally, in the same manner that we’ve seen that the Producer of the Film possesses a clear “motto”, “message” of “Goal” for his Film to attain – for the benefit of his “viewers”, so does the UCP steer the entire physical universe towards the fulfillment of its “Geulah Goal Perfected State” of the universe! And in the same manner that once the Film’s desired “motto” or “ultimate message” has been fulfilled, the Film inevitably reaches its “end”, so we realize, the UCP’s/UCR’s fulfillment of its “Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State of the universe” – signifies the “End of Time” for this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, in which its initial basic “Free-Will”/ “Wisdom” HCD (and more generally its three IKTHCD (“Blueprint Plan”) has been fulfilled!

A Characterization of the Current “End of Time: A Geulah Goal Perfected State” of the Universe!

The significant (and “exciting”) point (to be noted) is that with Twenty-First Century’s Theoretical Physics acceptance of the New “G-D’s Physics” (as the New Scientific Paradigm), we’ve reached the actual “consummation” of the entire physical universe’s “origination”, “development” and “attainment” of its “Ultimate Geulah Perfected State”! In other words, since the initial IKTHCD “Blueprint Plan” for the creation- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe, was all “pre-planned” by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR – all in order to “reach” and “fulfill” this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State” of the universe! And since, the fulfillment of this “Ultimate Geulah Goal” comprises a “Morally”, “Spiritually”, and even “Physically” “Perfected State” – in which Humanity (as a whole), and Science (within it) recognizes the “singularity” of this UCR, as “underlying” and indeed “transcending” the entire physical universe, and as being “characterized” based on its “sublime” Characteristics of “Morality”, “All-Goodness”, “Peace” and “Harmony” (which therefore affects- and manifests- Humanity’s existence and behavior); therefore, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein Humanity (and the physical universe as a whole) has already reached its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” – with the empirical validation and acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm (which points at the existence of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR characterized by these “sublime” characteristics)! So, now, we must ask the pertinent question: what does it “mean” that Humanity (Science and the whole universe) – have reached this “End of Time: Geulah Goal Perfected State” of the universe!? First of all, we realize that since the whole “motivation”, and “driving force” of the singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP was to “steer” Humanity (and in fact, the whole universe) towards this “Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State”; A “Perfected” (“Morally”, “Spiritually” and even “Physically”) “Geulah State” – in which the “singularity” and “oneness” of this UCR/UCP, together with its “intrinsic-special” characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” will be recognized (and “lived-by”) the whole Humanity! Therefore, this “End of Time: Geulah Perfected State” of the universe implies a real fundamental change in our world (as we “know it”)! Another (simple daily) “metaphor” is given relating to our “commonsense understanding” wherein we know that any (“mentally-balance”) human-being will not take their “right-hand” to “inflict pain” (G-D forbid) on their “left hand” (simply because, they are both integral-parts of themselves)! In the same manner (it is suggested), that this “End of Time Perfected Geulah State” of the universe will bring Humanity (as a whole), and each one of us (individually) to completely “alter” our “attitude” and “behavior” towards each other! Once Science (and the whole of Humanity!) recognizes that we’re all “integral parts” of this singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR), and that this singular higher-ordered UCR is characterized by all of these “sublime” characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Oneness”, “Peace” and “Harmony” – then we inevitably cannot (any longer) “inflict

pain” or “suffering” upon each other, but are rather “propelled” to “assist” and “care” for each other (e.g., just like in the “simple daily metaphor” given above, wherein we would not consider inflicting “pain” or “suffering” with our “right hand” upon our “left hand”!)

Second, our whole (basic) understanding of the existence, true nature, and development of the entire physical universe would undergo a profound (major) “metamorphosis”: we would realize that the universe does not exist as an “independent-material” reality, but is rather only a “transient-phenomenal” manifestation of this singular UCR Reality! As such, we also realize that the (hitherto) development of the entire physical universe has only been “geared” towards the fulfillment of this singular (higher-ordered) UCR’s “Geulah Perfected Goal State” of Humanity and the universe, and hence, that upon “fulfilling” this “Geulah Goal Perfected State” (of Humanity and the entire physical universe) that the future existence of Humanity (and the universe) would be characterized (purely) by this “Morally”, “Spiritually” and even “Physically” “Perfected Geulah Goal State”! It is perhaps, therefore, appropriate to end this (significant) article with the great Prophecy of both Maimonides and Isaiah, who both prophesized that towards the “end of time” the whole world’s occupation: “would be to “know” That singular “G-D Reality” (e.g., in “G-D’s Physics” scientific terms”: the singular, higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Reality”! And that at that “end of time” period, there would be no “wars”, wherein all “swords” will be turned into “ploughs” [8-13].

Dedication

This article is dedicated to the Great Lubavitacher Rabbi, to my beloved (diseased) Mother, Dr. Tirzah Bentwich (Bat Yitzchak), my beloved wife Shulamit Bentovish, my children: Shoham and Nethanel Yosef, and Neomy Tirzah Shualmit, and to the whole of Humanity: may this (consuming) article assist Humanity to “open our eyes” and see the singular Reality which is characterized by such “sublime” characteristics as “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”, and lead the world (at large) to begin “realizing” and “living” this “Perfected Geulah State”!

References

1. Pohl R, Antognini A, Nez F, Amaro FD, Biraben F, et al. (July 2010).

"The size of the proton" (PDF). *Nature*. 466: 213–216.

- Karr, J.; Hilico, L. (2012). "Why three-body physics does not solve the proton-radius puzzle". *Physical Review Letters*. 109 (10).
- Onofrio, R. (2013). "Proton radius puzzle and quantum gravity at the Fermi scale". *EPL*. 104 (2).
- Zyga, Lisa (November 26, 2013). "Proton radius puzzle may be solved by quantum gravity". *Phys.org*. Retrieved September 2, 2016.
- Dahia, F; Lemos, A.S. (2016). "Is the proton radius puzzle evidence of extra dimensions?". *European Physical Journal*. 76 (8): 435. arXiv:1509.08735. Bibcode:2016EPJC...76..435D. doi:10.1140/epjc/s10052-016-4266-7. S2CID 118672005.
- Liu Y, McKeen D, Miller GA (2016). "Electrophobic Scalar Boson and Muonic Puzzles". *Physical Review Letters*. 117 (10).
- Lestone, J.P. (4 October 2017). Muonic atom Lamb shift via simple means (Report). Los Alamos Report. Los Alamos National Laboratory. LA-UR-17-29148.
- Bentwich, J. (2012a) "Harmonizing Quantum Mechanics and Relativity Theory". *Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics*, Intech (ISBN 979-953-307-377-3), Chapter 22: 515-550.
- Bentwich, J. (2012b) "Theoretical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory". *Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics*, (ISBN 979-953-307-3773), Chapter 23: 551-598.
- Bentwich, J. (2013b). "The Theoretical Ramifications of the Computational Unified Field Theory". *Advances in Quantum Mechanics* (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7), Chapter 28: 671-882.
- Kuhn, Thomas S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1st ed.). University of Chicago Press. pp. 172. LCCN 62019621.
- Pohl R, et al. (2016a). "Laser spectroscopy of muonic deuterium". *Science*. 353: 669–673.
- Pohl R, et al. (16 September 2016b) "Proton-radius puzzle deepens". *CERN Courier*. After our first study came out in 2010, I was afraid some veteran physicist would get in touch with us and point out our great blunder. But the years have passed, and so far nothing of the kind has happened.

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